

Prevalence and Sensitivity Pattern of MRSA against Gentamycin, Vancomycin & Ciprofloxacin, in Indoor and OPD Patients of Holy Family Hospital

Furqan Ali Taj,¹ Faisal Javed,¹ Muhammad Soban Saeed,¹ Sofia Khan,³ Behzad Masood,¹ Afzaal Aleem Khan,¹ Muhammad Usman,¹ Rabi Zubair,¹ Muhammad Umair,¹ Muhammad Omer Farooq Khan²

¹House Officer, Rawalpindi Medical University

²House Officer, Punjab Medical University

³Supervisor and Associate Professor, Pathology Department, Rawalpindi Medical University

Abstract

Background: Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is a common pathogen which has increased both morbidity and mortality in hospitals and out-door patients.

Objective: Aim of our study is to measure prevalence of MRSA in in-door patients and out-door patients, as well as its sensitivity against gentamycin, vancomycin and ciprofloxacin.

Methods: A sample of 194 *S. aureus* was taken retrospectively from Pathology lab of a tertiary care hospital. MRSA was identified and further subjected against gentamycin, vancomycin and ciprofloxacin.

Result: 65.9% of *S. aureus* isolates were MRSA. 22.7%, 35.7%, 99.1% of MRSA were susceptible to ciprofloxacin, gentamycin and vancomycin, respectively. 75.8% MRSA was from pus samples. 66% MRSA was from in-door patient department (IPD).

Conclusion: MRSA was more prevalent in IPD. MRSA prevalence is escalating. Vancomycin is losing its effectiveness against MRSA as one resistant case was found. Inappropriate use and unprofessional prescriptions for antibiotics can be the main cause. Proper legislative action is required to keep in control the prescriptions for antibiotics.

Keywords: Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, Bacterial drug resistance, Antimicrobial drugs

Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus discovered in 1880 colonized 27% of healthy human population in US.¹ It causes a spectrum of diseases from skin infections like abscesses, cellulitis, impetigo, boils and scalded skin syndrome to various pyogenic infections like

endocarditis, septic arthritis and osteomyelitis. It is also one of the most common causes of Hospital Acquired pneumonia, septicemia and surgical wound infections.¹

Penicillin was initially effective against *S. aureus* but resistance against penicillin emerged in penicillinase producing strain within 15 years of Penicillin discovery.¹ In 1961, two years after Methicillin introduction, first case of Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was discovered.¹ MRSA poses resistance to almost the entire class of β -lactam agents¹ and is now found worldwide as Healthcare Acquired Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (HA-MRSA) & Community Acquired Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-MRSA).² In US hospitals, in 2003, 64% of *S. aureus* isolated in ICU was MRSA.² During 2003-2004, in US, nasal colonization by *S. aureus* accounted for 29%, of which MRSA colonized <1.5%.² MRSA is showing remarkable resistance against Ciprofloxacin.² 43 years after Vancomycin discovery,² Vancomycin-intermediate *S. aureus* (VISA) was identified from Japan in 1996.² There has been a little increase in both VISA and Vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus* (VRSA) since then.² Gentamicin resistance in MRSA is reported in up to 72-88% isolates in different European hospitals.²

Summarizing the increasing prevalence in Pakistan: MRSA was reported as 5% in 1989¹ & 61% in 2002.¹ In another report, prevalence increased from 19.5% to 40% from 2001 to 2008.⁴ In Peshawar, there were 207 cases in 2009, increasing to 284 in 2010 and further increasing to 438 in 2011, which showed an increase of 111.6% in a period of two years from 2009 to 2011.¹ This poses an alarming situation. Prevalence of ciprofloxacin resistant MRSA was reported increasing from 87% in 1996 to 94% in 2003.⁵ In a study done in

Peshawar, in 2016, ciprofloxacin resistant MRSA prevalence was 80.2 %.

Gentamicin Resistant MRSA strains have been increasing steadily in Pakistan from 69% in 1996 to 88% in 2003.⁵ VRSA strains were detected in Lahore in 4% isolates of MRSA in 2004.⁵

In Empirical treatment, while vancomycin is the drug of choice for MRSA, ciprofloxacin and gentamycin (along with β -lactam antibiotics) are still two of the most commonly prescribed and used antibiotics in Pakistan for indications like respiratory tract infections, septicemia, pneumonia, skin infections, osteomyelitis, urinary tract infections among many others. *S. aureus* is one of the main pathogens associated with these diseases.² There is very limited data available on prevalence and susceptibility patterns of MRSA against these drugs in Pakistan which is not enough to understand the increasing antibiotic resistance in MRSA. Most of the studies done in Pakistan to check sensitivity of MRSA against these drugs date back to 2003-04. To devise a proper health plan and drug regimens for these resistant strains, more data is essential. Evaluation and gathering data on this topic is becoming imperative to prevent any further expansion in infection rates of MRSA which would put a huge drain on Pakistan's economy. Thus, it is very much needed and logical to conduct studies to gather data and make sense of the ever-changing pattern of antimicrobial resistance.

The objective of the study is to determine the prevalence of MRSA isolated from various samples at Pathology Lab of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. We have also studied susceptibility pattern of MRSA against antimicrobial agents viz. gentamycin, ciprofloxacin and vancomycin. Distribution of MRSA in OPD and IPD patients is also determined. This study will help clinicians to understand and realize the alarming rise in antimicrobial resistance and urge them to use antibiotics judiciously.

Methodology

This retrospective Cross-Sectional study, was conducted at Pathology Lab of Holy Family Hospital (HFH), Rawalpindi - a tertiary care hospital. Study population were those Out Patient Department (OPD) & In-patient Department (IPD) patients at HFH who had *Staphylococcus aureus* identified in their samples. Using confidence level 95% and confidence interval 7%, a sample size of 196 was calculated by WHO sample size calculator. A sample of 194 *S. aureus* isolates was collected for a period of 6 months (August

2017 to January 2018) using consecutive sampling technique.

Various samples from the study population were received and transferred to laboratory. MacConkey agar and Blood agar were used as culture media for growth of bacterial isolates. The samples were incubated overnight at 37°C under aerobic conditions. Macroscopic features of colonies i.e. yellow to cream color, 1-2 mm on Blood agar and 0.1-0.5 mm on MacConkey agar, gram positivity and catalase positivity were observed to identify *Staphylococci*. Coagulase test differentiated between Coagulase Positive *S. aureus* & Coagulase Negative *Staphylococci* (CoNS). Only *S. aureus* isolates were included in study, all other samples and repeat samples from the same patient were excluded.

The Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines were followed to check sensitivity against cefoxitin, ciprofloxacin and gentamycin (Table I).¹ The British Society for Antimicrobial Chemotherapy (BSAC) guidelines were used to check sensitivity against vancomycin.¹ Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was used to determine the susceptibility pattern. Isolates resistant to Cefoxitin were recognized as MRSA. The data was analyzed using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Results

Out of 194 *S. aureus* isolates, 128 (65.9%) were MRSA. Majority of *Staphylococcus aureus* were found in pus (80.4%) while urine has least number of isolates (Table II). Similarly, majority of MRSA was also present in pus (75.8%) followed by respiratory, blood, HVS and urine samples (Table III). All *S. aureus* isolates were tested against cefoxitin, vancomycin, gentamycin & ciprofloxacin. Sensitivity and resistance data of MRSA & methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) is provided in Table IV. A majority (66%) of MRSA isolates were from IPD (Table V).

Table I: Antibiotic concentration and zone diameter breakpoint used

Antibiotic	Zone diameter breakpoint (Resistant)
Cefoxitin (30 μ g)	\leq 21 mm
Ciprofloxacin (5 μ g)	\leq 15 mm
Gentamycin (30 μ g)	\leq 12 mm

Table II: Distribution of S. aureus in various samples.

Sample	S. aureus (No.)	S. aureus (% out of n = 194)
Pus	156	80.4
Respiratory	14	7.2
Blood	11	5.7
HVS	9	4.6
Urine	4	2.1
Total	194	

Table III: Distribution of MRSA in various samples.

Sample	MRSA (No.)	MRSA (% of n = 128)
Pus	97	75.8
Respiratory	14	10.9
Blood	9	7
HVS	4	3.12
Urine	4	3.12
Total	128	99.94

Table IV: Sensitivity & Resistance of MRSA & MSSA against Gentamycin, Vancomycin & Ciprofloxacin.

Species	Gentamycin	
	Sensitive	Resistant
MRSA	35.7%	64.3%
MSSA	73.3%	26.6%
	Vancomycin	
	Sensitive	Resistant
MRSA	99.1%	0.82%
MSSA	100%	0%
	Ciprofloxacin	
	Sensitive	Resistant
MRSA	22.7%	77.3%
MSSA	22.2%	77.7%

Table V: Distribution of S. aureus & MRSA in OPD & IPD.

	S. aureus (%)	MRSA (%)
IPD	83.6%	66%
OPD	16.4%	33.3%

Discussion

In 2002, Hafiz S. et al showed that prevalence of MRSA, in major cities of Pakistan, ranged between 2-61%. Same study showed that prevalence of MRSA in Islamabad/Rawalpindi was 46%.¹⁴ Present study identified 65.9% isolates as MRSA, which in

accordance to other studies conducted in Pakistan, is very alarming.

Present study showed that major source for S. aureus was pus which accounted for 80.4%, while respiratory, blood, HVS and urine samples collectively accounted for 19.6%. Similarly, out of 128 MRSA isolates, major source was pus accounting for 75.8%, while rest of the samples accounted for 24.14%. It is comparable to other studies by Ahmed K R et al,⁷ Sumaira Kanwal et al¹ & Bukhari MH et al.¹⁹ Quite interestingly, this study showed that S. aureus isolates from respiratory and urine sample has more methicillin resistant strains than other samples. 100% of S. aureus isolated from respiratory and urine samples were MRSA, followed by 81.8%, 62.2% and 44.4% from blood, pus & HVS, respectively. This is contrary to the study conducted by Bukhari MH et al.¹⁹

MRSA showed least sensitivity against ciprofloxacin i.e. 22.7%. This is in accordance to the study by Syeda Q. Ali et al¹ & Butt T et al.¹⁷ Sensitivity against gentamycin was 35.7% which is in accordance with Butt T et al¹⁷ and international studies.^{8,12} Sensitivity against vancomycin was 99.1%. One case of MRSA was found to be vancomycin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (VRSA). Presence of one VRSA case in 194 S. aureus is very alarming. VRSA strains are increasing steadily in Pakistan. This study is in accordance with the local studies. Distribution of S. aureus and MRSA is more in IPD compared to OPD (Table IV). This result is in accordance with local study by Ahmed K R et al.²² This increased distribution of MRSA in IPD can be because of long-term admission of patients which exposes them to variety of pathogens, which are able to transfer resistance through horizontal gene transfer.¹⁰

Conclusion

This study shows that prevalence of MRSA is increasing at a very alarming rate and so is its resistance against other antibiotics. Most worrisome is the fact that VRSA strains are emerging. There is an increase in MRSA in IPD, which should be decreased by keeping admittance period of the IPD patients to a minimum. Overuse and misuse of antibiotics by either self-medication or unprofessional prescriptions by doctors should be prevented. Improved diagnostic techniques can help in targeted treatment.

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Authors Contributions

Fuqan Ali Taj: Wrote manuscript, conceived and designed analysis, **Faisal Javed:** Performed analysis, **Muhammad Soban Saeed, Afzal Aleem Khan, Behzaad Mehmood:** Data collection, **Sofia Khan:** Conception of Idea, **Rabi Zubair, Muhammad Umair, Muhammad Omer Farooq Khan:** Literature Review

How to Cite this Article: Ali Taj, F., Javed, F., Soban Saeed, M., Khan, S., Masood, B., Aleem Khan, A., Usman, M., Zubair, R., Umair, M., & Omer Farooq Khan, M. (2019). Prevalence and Sensitivity Pattern of MRSA against Gentamycin, Vancomycin & Ciprofloxacin, in Indoor and OPD Patients of Holy Family Hospital. *Journal of Rawalpindi Medical College*, 23(S-2), 115-118